

Recommended citation

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A Study of Information Literacy Skills of Engineering Undergraduates at the University of Moratuwa

Abstract

This research was conducted to investigate the status of information literacy skills of the undergraduates of the Engineering Faculty of the University of Moratuwa. The information skills test was administered to a stratified random sample of 189 Level 4 Engineering undergraduates representing all academic departments. The findings and implications of the research will be discussed.

1. Introduction

Information literacy has been recognized as the core literacy of the 21st century, underpinning all other forms of literacy and making them possible. This statement also posits the phenomenon as a core concept of the information society in the 21st century, indicating people's relentless need for information in order to achieve educational, social, occupational, and economic goals (Catts, 2005). The most commonly used definition of information literacy is an understanding and set of abilities enabling individuals to recognize when information is needed and have the ability to define, locate, evaluate, and use the needed information effectively. Hence, people are considered to be information literate when they need information, and are then able to identify, locate, evaluate, organize, and effectively use the information to address and help resolve personal, job-related, or broader social issues and problems (Catts and Lau, 2008).

When undergraduates passing out from universities are seen as tomorrow's workers, all undergraduates have to be information literate, and such people are a valuable asset to any employer. It is widely recognized in the developed world that information literacy has to be taught to students during their undergraduate programmes. Universities in developed countries have already refocused their undergraduate curriculum to address information literacy skills. However, none of the universities in Sri Lanka has attempted to investigate the information literacy skill levels of undergraduates, to date.

In the above context, this research was conducted to investigate the status of information literacy skills of undergraduates of the University of Moratuwa.

2. Methodology

2.1 Measures

Information literacy skills of undergraduates were surveyed using 25 multiple-choice questions (MCQ) developed for the study, addressing 8 skill sets and 4 information literacy standards. These 25 questionnaire items

in a matrix of skill set and information literacy standards are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The matrix of skill set and information literacy standards: questionnaire items

Standard \ Skill	Determine the Nature & Extent of Information Needed	Accesses Needed Information Effectively & Efficiently	Evaluates Information & its Sources	Understands many of the economic, legal & social issues
Developing a Research Strategy (Skill1)	1, 3	2	-	-
Selecting, Finding Tools (Skill2)	5	4, 6	7	-
Searching (Skill3)	-	8, 9, 25	-	-
Using Finding Tool Features (Skill4)	-	10, 11, 12	-	-
Retrieving Sources (Skill5)	-	13, 14, 15	-	-
Evaluating Sources (Skill6)	-	-	16, 17, 18	-
Documenting Sources (Skill7)	-	19	-	20, 21
Understanding Economics, Legal & Social Issues (Skill8)	-	-	-	22, 23, 24

As shown in Table 1, Questions under Skill1 assess the ability of students in defining and articulating the need for information. Questions under Skill2 assess the ability of students in identifying a variety of types and formats of potential information sources and the costs and benefits of acquiring the

needed information. Questions under Skill3 assess the ability of students in accessing needed information effectively and efficiently using different search strategies. Questions under Skill4 assess students' knowledge of characteristics and features of different information sources. Questions under Skill5 is used to test the ways and means of retrieving information online or in person using a variety of methods according to the characteristics and features of information sources. Questions under Skill6 were focused on how students' evaluation of information and its sources, and how they can incorporate selected information into his or her knowledge base and value system. Questions under Skill7 test students' knowledge and experience on acknowledging information sources using appropriate documentation style. Questions under Skill8 were used to test the economic, legal, and social issues surrounding the use of information.

2.2 Sample and data analysis

A stratified random sample of 189 Level 4 Engineering undergraduates representing all academic departments responded. The majority of the students responded to the test in a classroom setting. Data was analyzed using SPSS, Statistical Program for Social Science (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Information literacy skill levels

Table 2 shows the matrix of information literacy skills and information literacy standards. The average score for each skill ranges from 0 to 1.

Table 2: Matrix of information literacy skills

Standard \ Skill	Determine the Nature & Extent of Information Needed	Accesses Needed Information Effectively & Efficiently	Evaluates Information & its Sources	Understands many of the economic, legal & social issues
Skill1	$\bar{X} = .33$ SD=.17	$\bar{X} = .50$ SD=.12	-	-
Skill2	$\bar{X} = .21$ SD=.40	$\bar{X} = .29$ SD=.33	$\bar{X} = .28$ SD=.44	-
Skill3	-	$\bar{X} = .55$ SD=.33	-	-
Skill4	-	$\bar{X} = .57$ SD=.28	-	-
Skill5	-	$\bar{X} = .64$ SD=.27	-	-
Skill6	-	-	$\bar{X} = .57$ SD=.28	-
Skill7	-	$\bar{X} = .39$ SD=.48	-	$\bar{X} = .47$ SD=.20
Skill8	-	-	-	$\bar{X} = .28$ SD=.30

Note: Maximum attainable=1.

Figure 1 shows means and standard deviations for each skill set. Composite mean scores were calculated for each of the eight skills investigated.

Figure 1: Information literacy skill levels

Note: Maximum attainable=1.

Level 4 Engineering undergraduates' performance on each skill set can be ordered as:

Highest scored

- Retrieving Sources (Skill5): $\bar{X} = .65$
- Using Finding Tool Features (Skill4): $\bar{X} = .58$
- Searching (Skill3): $\bar{X} = .48$
- Documenting Sources (Skill7): $\bar{X} = .49$
- Evaluating Sources (Skill6): $\bar{X} = .41$
- Developing a Research Strategy (Skill1): $\bar{X} = .39$
- Understanding Economic, Legal, and Social Issues (Skill8): $\bar{X} = .29$
- Selecting and Finding Tools (Skill2): $\bar{X} = .26$

Lowest scored

The overall performance of the Level 4 Engineering undergraduates had a mean score of 0.43 (SD=0.14). To make comparisons with the data of this study, the results of this study were converted to the same scale of 0 to 1000. Table 3 shows the results.

Table 3: Detailed description of information literacy skills

Standard \ Skill	University of Moratuwa
Developing a Research Strategy (Skill1)	389 ± 9
Selecting, Finding Tools (Skill2)	261 ± 20
Searching (Skill3)	479 ± 21
Using Finding Tool Features (Skill4)	576 ± 21
Retrieving Sources (Skill5)	647 ± 20
Evaluating Sources (Skill6)	409 ± 30
Documenting Sources (Skill7)	448 ± 19
Understanding Economics, Legal & Social Issues (Skill8)	287 ± 24

Note: Scores are placed on a scale ranging from 0 to 1000 with standard error.

To improve the level of information literacy skills of undergraduates, universities across the world, to date, use two main strategies. First, placing information literacy skills on the same level as subject skills, thereby communicating to the students that these are important to be learned. However, exactly where in the curriculum these skills should be included has been largely a local decision. Second, creating a separate “information literacy skills course”.

Though the findings of this study on the status of information literacy skills of undergraduates of the University of Moratuwa imply the need of formulating strategies to improve information literacy skills. However, formulating strategies to improve information literacy skills of the undergraduates of the University of Moratuwa is beyond the scope of this study.

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